

STUDY OF STUDENTS' STUDY MOTIVES

Karimjonova Yoqutxon

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, psychology department,
teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7835215>

Annotatsiya : maqolada kasbiy ta'lim jarayonida shakllana boshlaydi va uning muhim mezonini psixologiya fakulteti talabalari o'rtasida mazmunli hayotiy yo'nalishlarning yuqori darajada shakllanishi, hamda ta'lim va kasbiy faoliyatning ichki motivlarining ustunligi hisoblanadinishi, talabalarining o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishlari ya'ni o'quv motivlari, ularni o'rganish, olimlarning ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari, talabalarni o'quv motivlarini amaliy o'rganish borasida tadqiqot ishlari jadvallar asosida bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar : motiv, motivatsiya, intilish, ong, faoliyat, ehtiyoj, psixolog, ta'lim muassasa, kasbiy.

Аннотация: статья начинает формироваться в процессе профессионального образования, и ее важным критерием является высокий уровень сформированности смысложизненных ориентиров у студентов факультета психологии, преобладание внутренних мотивов учебной и профессиональной деятельности, интерес к учебе или учебные мотивы, их изучение, научно-исследовательские работы ученых, практическое изучение учебных мотивов студентов описаны на основе таблиц.

Ключевые слова: мотив, мотивация, стремление, сознание, деятельность, потребность, психолог, образовательное учреждение, профессионал.

Abstract: the article begins to form in the process of professional education, and its important criterion is the high level of formation of meaningful life directions among students of the faculty of psychology, and the predominance of internal motives of education and professional activity, students' interest in studying or educational motives, their study, scientific research works of scientists, practical study of students' educational motives are described on the basis of tables.

Key words: motive, motivation, aspiration, consciousness, activity, need, psychologist, educational institution, professional.

Today, the need for qualified psychologists has increased dramatically due to the demands of practice. Without the participation of a psychologist, it is difficult to imagine the effective work of organizations that ensure the mental well-being of students in various educational institutions. In addition, a qualified psychologist is indispensable for conducting all kinds of examinations, as well as for the rehabilitation of people suffering from various diseases. Of course, only a person with high professional and personal training for the work of a psychologist is able to provide qualified psychological help. Such readiness begins to form in the process of professional education, and its important criterion is the high level of formation of meaningful life directions and the predominance of internal motives of education and professional activity among students of the faculty of psychology.

A.A.Rean and V.A.Yakunin's "Methodology for diagnosing students' educational motivation" (modified by N.S.Badmayeva) The purpose of the methodology is to study the motivations of students' educational activities. This research methodology is used to study the hierarchy of motives of educational and professional activity of psychology students and to identify the most important and least important motives in it. The technique involves sorting the following motifs from least important to most important according to their importance to the topic:

The methodology was developed based on the questionnaire of A.A.Rean and V.A.Yakunin. To the 16 statements of the above questionnaire, statements describing the motivations of education highlighted by V.G. Leontiev and statements describing the motivations of education obtained by N.T. Badmaeva as a result of a survey of students and schoolchildren were added. These are:

communicative, professional, educational and cognitive, broad social motives, as well as creative self-realization, failure and reputation avoidance motives.

➤ O'quv faoliyati motivatsiyasini o'rganish (Y.A.Kalinina) anketasi

Maqsad: anketa metodologiyasidan foydalangan holda ta'lim faoliyati motivatsiyasini o'rganish.50 ta savoldan iborat anketa ta'lim faoliyatining dominant motivlarini aniqlashga qaratilgan va 5 ta motivning miqdoriy tavsifini bilib olish imkonini beradi.

1) maqsadga erishish zarurati;

2) ta'lim faoliyatining raqobatbardoshligi zarurati;

3) o'z-o'zini takomillashtirish ehtiyojlari;

4) muloqot va jamoaviy faoliyatga bo'lgan ehtiyojlar;

5) ta'lim faoliyati jarayonidan tashqarida yangi bilimlarni o'zlashtirish zarurati.

➤ O'quv motivatsiyasining yo'nalganligini aniqlash (T.D.Duboviskaya) metodikasi.

It is customary to distinguish between different motives of learning, in particular, external and internal motives. L. M. Friedman describes their difference as follows: "If the motives that motivate a given activity are not related to it, then they are called external to this activity; if the motives are directly related to the activity itself, it is called "ulrichki". A motive is internal if it corresponds to the purpose of the activity. In other words, educational activity based on the conditions, mastering the content of the subject is both a motive and a goal at the same time. Internal motives are related to the subject's need for knowledge, pleasure from the process of knowledge. Mastering the educational material serves as the goal of learning, in this case it begins to take on the character of educational activity. And the student materially enters into the process of knowing, and this gives him emotional satisfaction. The superiority of internal motivation is characterized by its manifestation. in the process of educational activity, educational activity becomes external motivation under the condition of mastering the activity of students. The content of the subject is not a goal, but a means to achieve other goals. It can be a good grade (certificate, diploma), scholarships, praise, recognition by peers, obeying the teacher's demands, etc.

Knowledge with external motivation is not the goal of education, the student is away from the learning process. For the studied student, subjects are not internalized, do not have internal motivation, and the content of educational subjects does not become a personal value. A teacher who is interested in increasing the efficiency of his activity naturally pays attention to the motivation of learning and tries to activate it. at a high level, but at the same time, there is a lack of methodological tools that allow determining the current level of student motivation

and its dynamics when choosing different forms, teaching methods and subject content. developed, it can be used in the educational process and serves as a basis for increasing the effectiveness of teaching. The method of Spearman and Pearson correlation analysis was used for quantitative processing of the obtained data, since the available indicators are measured on an ordinal scale.

For the first time in the empirical study of students' learning motivations, the method of diagnosing students' learning motivation (A.A. Rean and V.A. Yakunin's method) N.S. Badmayeva's modification) was used. It was held among the students of the 1st and 3rd year of applied psychology of the university. Separate results are issued on 7 scales. These scales are:

1. Communicative motives;
2. Avoidance motives;
3. Reputation motives;
4. Professional motives;
5. Motives of creative self-realization;
6. Educational motives;
7. Social motives:

According to it, we can see the differences between the courses in each scale. On the scale of communicative motives, communication showed a higher result in the 1st courses than in the 3rd courses. Because 1st-year students are a newly formed group, they are more interested in communication and getting to know each other than 3rd-year students. In the scale of avoidance motives, we can also see the superiority of 1st year students. Avoidance motives are considered to avoid failure, and situations such as getting low grades in classes and failing exams or not being able to achieve the expected result have a strong impact on 1st year students.

Diagram 1

Differences in the average values of the first and third courses according to A.A.Rean and V.A.Yakunin's "Methodology for diagnosing students' educational motivation" (N.S.Badmayeva's modification).

According to it, we can see the differences between the courses in each scale. On the scale of communicative motives, communication showed a higher result in the 1st courses than in the 3rd courses. Because 1st-year students are a newly formed group, they are more interested in communication and getting to know each other than 3rd-year students. In the scale of avoidance motives, we can also see the superiority of 1st year students. Avoidance motives are considered to avoid failure, and situations such as getting low grades in classes and failing exams or not being able to achieve the expected result have a strong impact on 1st year students. For this reason, they have a high motivation to escape. In the scale of reputation motives, the results in the 1st courses are much higher than in the 3rd courses. After all, first-year students are at the first stage of their student life, the new environment is interesting for them, and they try to look prestigious in the eyes of others. For third-year students, it becomes normal and the opinion of others about them becomes less important. In the scale of professional motives, the result of the 1st year students showed a higher level than the 3rd year students. 3rd-year students change their interest and views on the profession during their studies, and it is possible that they may become interested in a field other than the one they are studying or work in a different field.

However, 1st-year students are relatively more interested in their field of study, and their motivation for the profession increases. The 5th scale is the motive of creative self-realization, and in contrast to this scale, the 3rd courses are dominant. So, the higher a student goes to a higher course, the more his thinking, worldview expands, and his self-awareness increases. Aesthetic taste expands, and interest in creating new things in the field of study increases. In the 1st courses, there is a strong desire for innovation in the field. In the scale of learning and

educational motives, with 0.6 points, there is a leadership in the 1st courses compared to the 3rd courses. It can be seen that the first-year students have a strong interest and need to study and gain knowledge. Our last scale is the scale of social motives, and in this scale, 1st-year students dominate. Because 1st-year students have a high score on the scale of communicative motives, and these motives are closely related to each other.

Medium-level internal motivation showed a high result in 1st courses. The high level of internal motivation is high in the 3rd year.

According to the results of the method of determining the direction of educational motivation (T.D. Duboviskaya), if we look at the differences between the sexes, a low level of internal motivation was not detected. The average level of internal motivation is higher in men, on the contrary, the high level of internal motivation prevails in women than in men.

According to the results of Y.A. Kalinina's questionnaire "Determining the motivation of educational activities", mutual differences between the courses on each scale were determined. low level was 8%, medium level was 81%, high level was 9%, and among third-year students, low level of internal motivation was 14%, medium level was 80%, high level was 2%. Relatively speaking, we can see that the average level of intrinsic motivation is similar in both courses. According to the results of Y.A. Kalinina's questionnaire "Determining the motivation of educational activity", mutual differences between the courses on each scale were determined. According to the results of Y.A. Kalinina's questionnaire "Determining the motivation of educational activities", mutual differences between the courses on each scale were determined. The third scale is the scale of self-improvement, according to which in the first years, the low level of internal motivation was 19%, the middle level was 69%, and the high level was 10%, and in the third year students, the low level of internal motivation was 19%, the middle level was 74%, and the high level was 3%.

At the same time, learning activities and mastering the content of the subject, subjects are not internalized for the student, they do not have internal motivation, and the content of educational subjects does not become a personal value.

The predominance of internal motivation is characterized by its manifestation. Educating a person, first of all, consists in developing a system of his needs and motives.

The motivation factor for successful study is stronger than the intelligence factor. Realization of the high importance of learning motivation for successful learning led to the definition of the principle of motivational support of the learning process. Among the various motivations for learning, in particular, external and internal

it is usual to distinguish motives. L. M. Friedman describes their difference as follows: "If the motives that motivate a given activity are not related to it, then they are called external to this activity; if the motives are directly related to the activity itself, they are called internal. A motive is internal if it corresponds to the purpose of the activity. That is, based on conditions, in today's constantly changing, dynamic world, it is not only teaching students knowledge, skills and abilities in subjects. At the same time, learning activities, mastering the content of the subject, the subjects are not internalized for the student, do not have internal motivation, and the content of the educational subjects does not become a personal value, and the student's personality as an active person in the future ensures social development, preservation and provision provides. Internal motives are related to the subject's need for knowledge, pleasure from the process of knowledge. Mastering the educational material

serves as the goal of learning, in this case it changes the nature of the educational activity. Under the condition of mastering, educational activity becomes external motivation. The motivation factor for successful study is stronger than the intelligence factor. Realization of the high importance of learning motivation for successful learning led to the definition of the principle of motivational support of the learning process. Among the various motivations for learning, in particular, external and internal

it is usual to distinguish motives. L. M. Friedman describes their difference as follows: "If the motives that motivate a given activity are not related to it, then they are called external to this activity; if the motives are directly related to the activity itself, they are called internal"

Learning motivation is internal if it corresponds to the purpose of the activity. In today's constantly changing, dynamic world, it is not only teaching the student knowledge, skills and abilities in subjects (some of them). in itself

for the student, subjects are not internalized, do not have internal motivation, and the content of educational subjects does not become a personal value.

In the method of determining the direction of educational motivation (T.D. Duboviskaya), almost no significant differences were found between gender and courses. However, according to the results, external motivation is higher in men, and on the contrary, internal motivation is higher in women. Also, the internal motive prevails in the 1st courses, and the external motive prevails in the 3rd courses.

Table 1

		Number of respondents	Average	t
Communicative motives	male	75	4,1200	-2,179*
	woman	115	4,3142	
Avoidance motives	male	75	3,5573	-2,367*
	woman	115	3,7809	
Reputation motives	male	75	4,0907	-3,722***
	woman	115	4,4296	
Professional motives	male	75	4,2640	-2,823**
	woman	115	4,4835	
Motives of creativity and self-realization	male	75	4,2107	-3,061***
	woman	115	4,4922	
Educational motives	male	75	3,9587	-,542
	woman	115	4,0078	
Social motives	male	75	4,3573	-2,637**
	ayol	115	4,5357	

Table 1: Results of correlational analysis between courses of A.A.Rean and V.A.Yakunin's "Methodology for diagnosing students' educational motivation" (N.S.Badmayeva's modification).

Significant differences between genders were found in the "Communicative motives" scale. According to him, it was proved that women have a higher need for communication and communication than men ($t=-2.367$; $p=0.05$;). A big difference was found between women and men in terms of "reputation-attention motives" ($t=-3.722$; $p=0.01$;). In this scale too, women's

desire to gain prestige and attention showed a much higher result. Also, women showed a high result in "Professional motives". ($t=-2.823$; $p=0.01$;). In the scale of "motives of creative self-realization" and in the scale of "social motives" higher differences and indicators were found in women than in men ($t=-2.637$; $p=0.01$;). No gender differences were found in the "Educational motives" scale. From this we can see the similarity of study motivations between women and men. If large and significant differences were found between other types of motives, it was shown that there is no difference between educational and educational motives, and this was proven by statistical analysis. So, we can see that educational motives do not depend on gender, on the contrary, the importance of other motives is strong.

Table 2: Results of correlational analysis between courses of A.A.Rean and V.A.Yakunin's "Methodology for diagnosing students' educational motivation" (N.S.Badmayeva's modification).

According to him, communicative motives are higher in the 1st courses than in the 3rd courses. Because 1st year students will be in the circle of new acquaintances, that is, new students, new teachers, new environment will not fail to have an effect on this. For this reason, their need for communication increases and interpersonal relations develop on their own. As a result of students exchanging information, communication increases. Avoidance motives also dominate in 1st courses compared to 3rd courses.

References:

1. Azizxo'jaeva N. N. Pedagogik texnologiyalar va pedagogik mahorat. –T.: O'z bekiston yozuvchilar uyushmasi Adabiyot jamg'armasi nashriyoti. 2006 y. 200b.
2. Abu Rayhon Beruniy. Feruza (Javohirlar haqida naql va hikoyatlar). – Toshkent: A.Qodiriy nomidagi nashriyot, 1993.
3. Axmedova M., Abdurahmonova N., Jumaev M. Matematika. 1-sinf uchun darslik. T.: "Turon-iqbol". 2008-yil.
4. Божович Л. И. Проблемы формирования личности. –М.: Воронеж 1997 г
5. Бондаренко С.М. Проблема формирование познавательного интереса при классно-групповом и программированном обучении: по материалам психолого-педагогической литературы. //Вопросы алгоритмизации и программирования обучения. /Под.ред. Л.Н.Ланды. Москва., 1973 г.
6. Burxonov S., Xudoyorov O', Norqulova Q. Matematika. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarining 3-sinfi uchun darslik. "Sharq" nashriyot matbaa aksiyadorlik kompaniyasi bosh tahririyati. – T.: 2012 yil. 208 bet.
7. Васильев И.А., Магомед Эминов М.Ш. Мотивация и контроль за действием. М. 1991 г. 143 с.